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OPHN functions in melanoma resistance.

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Citations

1. Wood, H., 2004. Spiny problems in MRX. Nature Reviews Neuroscience, 5(5), pp.341-341.
2. Fauchereau, F., Herbrand, U., Chafey, P., Eberth, A., Koulakoff, A., Vinet, M.C., Ahmadian, M.R., Chelly, J. and Billuart, P., 2003. The RhoGAP activity of OPHN1, a new F-actin-binding protein, is negatively controlled by its amino-terminal domain. Molecular and Cellular Neuroscience, 23(4), pp.574-586.